

Forestry plantations on rice bunds: farmers' perceptions and technology adoption

S.S. Bargali, S.P. Singh, S.K. Shrivastava, and S.S. Kolhe, Indira Gandhi Agricultural University, Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Anjora, P.O. Box 06, Durg 491001, Chhattisgarh, India

This study was conducted in Durg District, Chhattisgarh State, where about 8% of the area (0.87 million ha) is forested. The villagers collect wood products from forests for their daily needs (mainly fuel wood). This ruthless cutting of trees and shrubs to narrow the gap between supply and demand of forest products endangers biodiversity and sustainable development, thereby adversely affecting ecological restoration.

Rice, a main crop of this region, is cultivated on 0.37 million ha, mostly under rainfed conditions in Durg. About 8–10% of the rice is grown in huge bunds. Generally, the new bunds are used to grow upland crops for 1–2 years; subsequently, these bunds are left fallow. In Chhattisgarh, the trees growing naturally on bunds and boundaries form an important traditional agroforestry system, dominated by *Acacia nilotica* (Bargali et al 2004), a hardy species that provides fuel, fodder, small timber, and gum. The north and south bunds of these rice fields may be successfully used to grow suitable tree species without affecting light intensity and thereby productivity of the rice crop. The adoption of recommended tree species and management practices may give farmers more economic benefits and may reduce the pressure on government forests.

Eighty farmers were selected randomly from eight villages (10 from each) in three blocks (Durg,

Dhamdha, and Gunderdehi) of Durg District. The farmers were then categorized on the basis of landholding—22 large (those who own > 4 ha), 39 medium (2–4 ha), and 19 small farmers (1–2 ha). They attended 2–7-d training activities on technology components (see figure) and were given tree saplings of their choice (>10 each farmer) at the beginning of the kharif season. After 2 years, a field survey was done and semistructured interviews were conducted. Adoption indices (AI) were calculated. Reasons for adopting/not adopting the

technology were solicited. It was evident that farmers had equally adopted the plantation technique (av AI = 76.0) and planted trees on rice bunds (av AI = 76.3), followed by aftercare and management (av AI = 57) (see figure). The higher adoption of the technology components by all farmer categories reflected their need, area of interest, and awareness of technology benefits. Forestry nursery establishment was adopted by only 5.7% of the farmers probably because they were provided with saplings, which initially fulfilled their requirement. The highest

Technology adoption, by farmer category.

Species preferred by farmers for plantations.

Farmer category		
Small	Medium	Big
Bamboo (<i>Dandrocalamus strictus</i> Nees), eucalyptus (<i>Eucalyptus treticornis</i> Sm.)	Bamboo, eucalyptus, teak (<i>Tectona grandis</i> Linn.), khamar (<i>Gmelina arborea</i>)	Bamboo, eucalyptus, teak, khamar, sissoo (<i>Dalbergia sissoo</i> Roxb.)

average adoption of technologies was seen among large farmers (AI = 57.6), closely followed by medium farmers (AI = 51.2). Adoption was low among small farmers (AI = 33.6), as they had lesser landholding, limited resources, and moderate literacy.

Small landholders preferred only bamboo and *Eucalyptus* for bund and boundary plantations to meet their household requirements. Medium and large farmers preferred a number of species (see table) as they are into commercial production and they have better resources. Depommier et al (2002) articulated that the needs and strategies of small farmers usually correspond to

subsistence agriculture with low inputs and, interestingly, a high level of diversification, which includes tree products and services. The multipurpose use of species partly satisfies the basic needs of poor farmers.

The data on planted saplings showed the highest mortality (71.5%) in small landholder plantations. This may be attributed to their poor socioeconomic conditions, less irrigation, limited aftercare resources, and open grazing by animals (inasmuch as the areas were not fenced). Most small farmers worked off-farm after the rice season and had no time to care for their animals. The large farmers' awareness and

better management, care, and resources resulted in low mortality (28.8%) in their plantations.

References

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